

EARTH SCIENCES

POSSIBILITIES OF ANALYTICAL CONTINUATION OF GRAVITY AND ITS GRADIENTS FOR PREDICTION OF CROSS-SECTION

Isgandarov E.

Associate professor,

Department of "Geophysics" Azerbaijan State Oil and Industrial University (ASOIU), Azerbaijan, Baku

Jafarli L.

Master student,

Department of "Geophysics" Azerbaijan State Oil and Industrial University (ASOIU), Azerbaijan, Baku

ABSTRACT

This article explores the feasibility of analytically continuing gravity and its gradients for predicting a cross-section. This problem is known to be related to the inverse gravity problem, which is not uniquely solved. To reduce this ambiguity, it is necessary to utilize all a priori information, which can improve the efficiency of solving such a problem. To predict the cross-section of density heterogeneity in rocks based on gravity data, the full normalized gravity gradient is currently used, along with other methods. The Department of Geophysics developed an algorithm and the Force-Fortran program Gnorm, which calculates the full normalized gravity gradient in the lower half-space based on the observed gravity curve at the earth's surface along the profile. This article presents the results of processing model gravity curves to assess the feasibility of cross-section prediction.

Keywords: Gravity curve, Fourier transform, full normalized gradient, density inhomogeneity, number of harmonics.

Introduction

Numerous methods exist for characterizing gravity anomalies and determining the location and depth of anomaly-generating geological features and zones of density heterogeneities based on potential fields. Since the goal of the study is to locate local features in the sedimentary strata at shallow depths, these methods employ differential calculus to enhance the intensity of the potential anomaly from small features. Analytical downward continuation (analytical approximation) can be used to enhance the gravitational influence of features at shallow depths [1,2,13].

Analytical continuation into the lower half-space is a method used to estimate the field closer to the source, resulting in better resolution of rock distribution in subsurface layers. However, the usefulness of this process is limited by its sensitivity to noise, which also leads to false anomalies. After downward continuation, the signal (potential field anomaly) is amplified exponentially proportional to the spectral frequency. In the absence of false anomalies, the analytical continuation process is sufficiently well-defined, and in this case, there is no need to continue below the depth of the geological feature. In filtering terms, this is the use of high-pass filters. In the presence of a false anomaly, the high-frequency amplification is so strong that it almost completely obscures the main useful information. A low-pass Fourier filter can be used to filter out this type of noise. Furthermore, this results in signal blurring, negating the purpose of sharpening the image obtained by the analytical continuation process. Despite the above-mentioned problems, most geophysicists have long been interested in this methodology because it is important for exploration of mineral deposits. Furthermore, this method is a fast and cost-effective way to determine the initial depth of underground objects in areas where logging data is lacking [4].

An effectively executed analytical process of downward continuation can provide accurate information about the subsurface, which can improve interpretation efficiency. Furthermore, analytical continuation into the lower half-space can enhance both the horizontal and vertical components of the potential field anomaly, which can improve the efficiency of solving the geological problem of subsurface subsurface dissection based on density properties.

Finally, models are constructed using a range of modeling programs that incorporate gravity data, and the most appropriate number of harmonics in the Fourier decomposition of the signal is selected. It should be noted that normalizing the total gravity anomaly gradient by the mean value of the total calculated gravity field gradient helps minimize strong field perturbations associated with the downward propagation of gravity anomalies

Means and methods

As is well known, various methods exist for transforming gravity-magnetic data to separate a complex field into regional and local anomalies. Among these methods, the analytical continuation of the potential field into the lower half-space is of interest. The meaning and significance of this method are demonstrated below using computer calculations and graphical plots for examples of gravity field models. Of particular interest is the concept of the full normalized gradient (FNG) method, which involves Fourier transforming the observed gravity curve, analytically continuing it into the lower half-space at various depths, and calculating the full normalized gravity gradient. Using this technique, FNG values can be calculated in the region containing density inhomogeneities corresponding to geological structures. Thus, the two-dimensional FNG curve of gravity anomalies is determined by the following formula (Berezkin, 1973):

$$G(x, z) = \frac{\sqrt{(g_x(x, z))^2 + (g_z(x, z))^2}}{\frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=0}^M \sqrt{(g_x(x, z))^2 + (g_z(x, z))^2}} \quad (1)$$

where $g_x(x, z) = \frac{\pi}{L} \sum_{n=1}^N n B_n \sin \frac{n\pi x}{L} e^{\frac{n\pi z}{L}}$ is the horizontal gradient of gravity at depth z ; $g_z(x, z) = \frac{\pi}{L} \sum_{n=1}^N n B_n \sin \frac{n\pi x}{L} e^{\frac{n\pi z}{L}}$ is the vertical gradient of gravity at depth z ; L is the summation base; N is the maximum number of harmonics; M is the number of points on the base L ; n is the coefficient number.

The Geophysics Department of ASOIU developed the Force-Fortran program Gnorm, which calculates the gravity gradient at various depths and was tested using a high-precision profile intersecting the Muradkhanly uplift [3, 6, 8, 10, 11]. In many studies, the number of harmonics (N) is typically determined by trial and error, and the use of additional data, such as drilling data, depends on the problem conditions and data characteristics. In our opinion, it is necessary to use any a priori geological and geophysical information. In addition, it is necessary to consider the intensity and size of the anomaly of the full normalized gravity gradient. In this regard, we performed an analytical continuation of the gravity field of two-dimensional homogeneous cylinder models to their depth [5, 7, 12].

Results and discussion

At the beginning, we performed an analytical continuation of the gravity field from the model of a two-dimensional cylinder with a radius of 1 km located at a depth of 4 km using the formula:

$$V_z = \frac{2G\lambda z}{(\xi-x)^2 + (\zeta-z)^2}, \quad (2)$$

where G is the gravitational constant; λ is the linear density of the cylinder; z is the depth of the center of a homogeneous cylinder; ξ, ζ are the coordinates of the center of gravity of a horizontal cylinder; x is the abscissa of the point of calculation of V_z on the profile;

z is the ordinate of the point of calculation of V_z on the profile.

For this purpose, the Force-Fortran program Vzsyl was compiled based on formula (2). The compiled initial data was entered into the Vzsyl program. The results of the analytical continuation of the field from a two-dimensional circular horizontal cylinder model to depths of 1-5 km in mGal units are shown below (Fig. 1). As can be seen, with increasing depth of continuation, the gravity values increase, and at a depth of 4 km ("special point") the value of V_z becomes equal to infinity. Based on the obtained results, gravity curves corresponding to different depths were constructed. The amplitude of the gravity curve corresponding to the depth of the cylinder center was conditionally taken to be equal to 10 mGal (instead of infinity). As can be seen, after passing through the "special point", the values of the gravity curve decrease and therefore the V_z curves at depths of 3 and 5 km coincide (Fig. 2). The same picture is observed in the diagram we compiled of the analytical continuation into the lower half-space of the gravity field from a two-dimensional cylinder, which also lies at a depth of 4 km (Fig. 3). Of great interest are the results of our analytical continuation into the lower half-space of the full normalized gravity gradient from a two-dimensional cylinder located at a depth of 4 km. As can be seen in the figure, the full normalized gravity gradient was calculated for a number of harmonics of 10, 20 and 30. The optimal number of harmonics was 30, when the maximum of the total normalized gradient coincided with the cylinder's depth of 4 km. When choosing the optimal number of harmonics, the size and intensity of the total normalized gradient must also be taken into account (Fig. 4-7).

MH is the maximum depth of the gravity curve extension in km; X_0 and Z_0 are the coordinates of the center of gravity of the circular cylinder in km; R is the radius of the cylinder; N is the number of points on the gravity curve profile; AK is the coefficient in the formula for calculating the vertical component of gravity from the cylinder.

MH= 5	X0= 5.0	R= 1.0	Z0= 4.0	N= 10	AK= 8.4				
0.34	0.47	0.65	0.84	0.93	0.84	0.65	0.47	0.34	0.25
0.42	0.65	1.05	1.68	2.10	1.68	1.05	0.65	0.42	0.29
0.49	0.84	1.68	4.20	8.40	4.20	1.68	0.84	0.49	0.32
0.52	0.93	2.10	8.40	∞	8.40	2.10	0.93	0.52	0.34
0.49	0.84	1.68	4.20	8.40	4.20	1.68	0.84	0.49	0.32

Fig. 1. Results of analytical extension of the gravity field from a two-dimensional homogeneous cylinder model to depths of 1-5 km

1- V_z curve at a depth of 1 km; 2- V_z curve at a depth of 2 km; 3- V_z curve at a depth of 3 km; V_z curve at a depth of 4 km; V_z curve at a depth of 5 km (V_z curves at depths of 3 and 5 km coincide).

Fig. 2. Curves of analytical continuation of the gravity field from the model of a two-dimensional homogeneous cylinder to depths of 1-5 km

Fig.3. Results of analytical continuation of the gravitational field in the lower half-space

Fig.4. Field of the full normalized gravity gradient from the model of circular cylinder (number of harmonics 10)

Fig.5. Field of the full normalized gravity gradient from the model of circular cylinder (number of harmonics 20)

Fig.6. Field of the full normalized gravity gradient from the model of circular cylinder (number of harmonic)

Fig.7. Field of the full normalized gravity gradient from the model of circular cylinder (number of harmonics 30)

Conclusions:

1. An analysis of the analytical continuation of the gravity field into the lower half-space was performed to predict the cross-section of density heterogeneity in rocks. A homogeneous model of a circular horizontal cylinder was created, and the vertical gravity field along the profile was calculated using the Vzysl program developed in Force-Fortran.

2. Using the Force-Fortran program Vzysl, an analytical continuation of the Vz curves from a circular horizontal cylinder model to depths of 1–5 km with a

1-km step was performed. The increase in gravity values and the behavior of the gravity field itself as they approach a "special point" are shown.

3. The values of the full normalized gravity gradient at various depths (0-7) km were calculated using the Force-Fortran GNORM program developed at the Department to assess the feasibility of analytically extending the full gravity gradient for predicting density heterogeneity. Using the Surfer program, sections of the full normalized gradient were constructed for different numbers of harmonics in the Fourier decomposition. The optimal number of harmonics was estimated to improve forecast accuracy.

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